

Storylines of projected summer warming in Iberia using atmospheric circulation, soil moisture and sea surface temperature as drivers of uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the uncertainty of future summer warming over Iberia using storylines constructed from climate model simulations of the Climate Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6. Unlike prior storyline approaches focusing on remote drivers and global teleconnections of atmospheric circulation, we use regional factors that directly influence summer temperatures: ridging activity, soil moisture and Mediterranean sea surface temperature. These drivers explain a substantial portion of the observed variability across climate models, with ridging activity and soil moisture showing the strongest influence on Iberian warming. Under a high radiative forcing scenario (SSP5–8.5), the storylines of Iberian warming based on these two drivers range between 7 and 9 °C for the end of the 21st century. The storyline leading to the largest warming is characterised by a drying out of the soil conditions and an increase in the anticyclonic activity over Iberia. We find similar conclusions for simple extreme heat indicators, though the approach struggles with more complex heatwave metrics. We also propose a novel modification of the storyline approach to increase the data sample of climate responses by using different time intervals throughout the 21st century. This modification would allow the application of more complex statistical models, the exploration of non-linear relationships and the identification of other drivers shaping the regional climate projections.

1. Introduction

The global surface temperature was 0.95–1.20 °C higher in 2011–2020 than in the preindustrial period 1850–1900 (IPCC, 2023). This warming has resulted from human activities (mainly through the emissions of greenhouse gases) and is already affecting numerous extreme weather events and climatic conditions all over the world. As a consequence, there have been widespread negative impacts, including losses and damages to both the environment and human populations (Vicedo-Cabrera et al., 2021; Clarke et al., 2022; Newman and Noy, 2023). The upward trend in global mean temperature is expected to persist in the near term, primarily due to increasing carbon dioxide

concentration in most considered future scenarios (IPCC, 2023). The projected global warming for 2081–2100 ranges from 1.0 to 1.8 °C for a low emissions scenario to 3.3–5.7 °C for a very high emissions scenario (IPCC, 2023).

The range of uncertainty is potentially much larger at the regional than at the global level, partially due to a greater influence of model resolution, parameterisations and natural climate variability (Hawkins and Sutton, 2011; Deser et al., 2012). Climate models have a spatial resolution limited by computational constraints, hampering their ability to adequately represent physical processes at small scales and local conditions affecting climate like topography, vegetation or water bodies (Randall et al., 2007; Feser et al., 2011; Soares et al., 2012). In addition,

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regional climate, particularly in mid-latitudes, is strongly modulated on a wide range of spatio-temporal scales by variability in the atmospheric and oceanic circulations, as they determine how heat and moisture are redistributed globally.

Previous studies have identified the Mediterranean region as a climate change “hot spot” because of the substantial drying and warming trends expected in the area (Giorgi, 2006; Michaelides et al., 2018). In particular, Iberia is projected to experience the largest precipitation decrease and the highest warming within this region (Lionello and Scarascia, 2018; Cos et al., 2022; Soares et al., 2023, 2024). The temperature change is expected to be especially pronounced in summer, which has already been experiencing several record-breaking heatwaves in the last years (Sánchez-Benítez et al., 2018; Sousa et al., 2019; Barriopedro et al., 2020; Serrano-Notivol et al., 2023). Despite the overall agreement on the sign of the projected change in temperature over Iberia, the magnitude of the change varies considerably among models (Cardoso et al., 2019; Herrera et al., 2020). A comprehensive study, using a multi-model ensemble of 196 regional and global climate models, investigated precipitation and temperature changes over Spain in the near future (Fernández et al., 2019). The authors concluded that the driving global climate model (GCM) is the main contributor to the uncertainty of the near-term projections simulated by the regional model ensemble.

As an alternative to the use of probabilistic projections to account for inter-model uncertainty, recent studies advocate approaches based on the construction of ‘storylines’ (Shepherd et al., 2018; Zappa, 2019). Each storyline represents an expected outcome based on one possible and physically self-consistent combination of climate change responses in well-known drivers of regional climate (Zappa and Shepherd, 2017). These storylines span the range of uncertainty within multi-model ensembles, helping provide further insight into the driving physical factors and their regional implications. Several studies have employed this approach to characterise the climate change uncertainty of different regional indicators (Garrido-Perez et al., 2022; Mindlin et al., 2020, 2021; Schmidt and Grise, 2021; Ghosh and Shepherd, 2023; Monerie et al., 2023), mostly focused on future precipitation and wind changes. Since these meteorological components are strongly driven by atmospheric circulation, whose response to climate change remains substantially uncertain (Woollings, 2010; Shepherd, 2014), dynamical storylines are typically generated based on the response of remote drivers and global teleconnections of atmospheric circulation.

The uncertainty associated with changes in thermodynamic components like temperature is strongly modulated by non-dynamical drivers. For instance, the state of soil and near water bodies are influencing factors for temperature, being also characterised by large inter-model uncertainty in future projections (Ma and Xie, 2013; Cheng et al., 2017; Trugman et al., 2018; Cheung et al., 2022). While dry soil conditions tend to reduce latent cooling and exacerbate land temperatures in transitional regions with soil moisture (SM) limited regimes (e.g. Fischer et al., 2007; Seneviratne et al., 2010; Gómez et al., 2015; Knist et al., 2017; Careto et al., 2018; Soares et al., 2019; Miralles et al., 2019), water bodies act as significant heat reservoirs and can potentially drive persistent air temperature anomalies over continental regions through heat exchanges with air masses and/or forced changes in atmospheric circulation (Black and Sutton, 2007; Della-Marta et al., 2007; Duchez et al., 2016; Reid and Hill, 2016; Barriopedro et al., 2023). In particular for Iberia, Jerez et al. (2012) and García-Valdecasas Ojeda et al. (2020) reported an amplification of the projected warming as a consequence of the future intensification in the positive SM-temperature feedback, highlighting the crucial contribution of SM to climate change projections in this region.

In this paper, we construct plausible storylines of summer temperature changes over Iberia for the 21st century based on drivers associated with the atmospheric circulation, the SM stress over the region and the Mediterranean Sea Surface Temperature (SST). Through this approach, we aim at 1) assessing how much of the projected warming can be

explained by the above-mentioned drivers, 2) evaluating the degree of influence exerted by the drivers both separately and combined, and 3) providing a quantitative analysis of future Iberian temperature changes for different storylines and levels of global warming.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the datasets (2.1), defines the drivers (2.2), and introduces the methodology employed to generate the storylines (2.3). Section 3 presents the results. First, we analyse the projected changes of the involved meteorological variables over Europe, including the multi-model mean (MMM) and the inter-model variability (3.1). Then, we determine the sensitivity of the projected temperature changes over Iberia to each driver’s response (3.2). Finally, we construct the storylines based on the combination of the drivers on which Iberian warming is most dependent (3.3). Section 4 discusses the results by considering additional applications and limitations of the methodology, namely the selection of the drivers (4.1), the extrapolation of the results to extreme temperatures (4.2), the assumption of linearity by the storyline approach (4.3), and the feedbacks between temperature changes and their drivers (4.4). Section 5 summarises the main findings and implications of this work.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Meteorological data

Daily maximum (Tmax) and mean (Tmean) temperature, as well as monthly 500 hPa geopotential height (Z500), SST, SM content within 0–10 cm below ground level, temperature at 250 and 850 hPa, and cloud cover fraction were obtained from an ensemble of 25 GCMs participating in the Climate Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) (Table S1; Eyring et al., 2016). We used the historical and shared socioeconomic pathway SSP5–8.5 experiments spanning the periods between 1981 and 2014 and 2015–2100, respectively. This ensemble encompasses all available CMIP6 models providing simulations of the required climate variables for the chosen time periods and emission scenario at the time of the development of the current study. While the GCMs ‘noresm2-lm’ and ‘mircoc6’ also meet these criteria, they are not included in the ensemble as their simulations showed considerable deviations from the overall ensemble distribution for some drivers (SST and SM, respectively). All simulated data were interpolated to a common grid with $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ horizontal resolution (144×72 grid points). To account for the inherent spatial variability of the data, we employed a conservative interpolation scheme (Jones, 1999) for SM, which minimizes the introduction of artificial values. For other climate variables (temperature, Z500, SST and cloud cover fraction), a bilinear interpolation scheme was used, considering the smoother spatial gradients of these variables. The results from the storyline framework are scaled by near-surface global-mean warming (GW) to separate the uncertainty in the pattern of the response from that in the GW level (see Section 2.3 for more details). Assuming that the amplitude of the climate responses depends mainly on the GW signal and not so much on the pathway of radiative forcing (pattern scaling assumption), the sensitivity of the results to the choice of the emissions scenario is generally very small (see e.g. Zappa and Shepherd, 2017). This way, the SSP5–8.5 scenario is employed in this work due to the higher number of available GCMs providing the required meteorological variables as compared to other high-forcing scenarios.

We have also extracted meteorological fields from the ERA5 meteorological reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) at $0.75^\circ \times 0.75^\circ$ horizontal resolution for two purposes: 1) to conduct an analogue analysis and 2) to assess the reliability of CMIP6 simulations for the historical period (see section 2.2). Daily Z500, SST and SM have been calculated by averaging four analysis values at the standard meteorological hours 00, 06, 12 and 18 for each day, whereas Tmax is computed as the maximum from all hourly temperature values. Furthermore, the SM content at 0–10 cm was linearly interpolated from the values of the 0–7 and 7–28 cm layers provided by ERA5. Reanalysis data have been interpolated in the same

way as for GCMs to the common grid with $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ horizontal resolution to allow a fair comparison with CMIP6 data.

2.2. Definitions of drivers

As mentioned previously, the interplay of the atmospheric circulation with the preceding conditions of SM or SST of nearby water bodies can influence the temperatures experienced over a certain region (Seneviratne et al., 2010; Reid and Hill, 2016; Miralles et al., 2019; Barriopedro et al., 2023; see additional references in the introduction). The following example for the heatwave of June 2017 illustrates these contributions for Iberia. From June 10 to 23, western and central Europe faced a heatwave that affected up to 8,000,000 km². During this event, Iberia experienced its most intense and persistent June heatwave so far in the reanalysis period, which was associated with a record-breaking subtropical ridge (Sánchez-Benítez et al., 2018). The large positive Z500 anomalies extended from northern Africa to central Europe (Fig. S1a) and led to mean daily Tmax anomalies close to 10 °C over some parts of Iberia (Fig. 1a). Besides the atmospheric circulation anomalies, there were outstanding SM deficits over southern and central Europe (Fig. S1b) and very warm SSTs in the western Mediterranean (WM) (Fig. S1c).

To account for the triggering role of the atmospheric circulation, we used the flow circulation analogue method, which identifies days with statistically similar circulation features and reconstructs a given meteorological variable based on the near surface conditions associated with the identified flow analogues (e.g. Jézéquel et al., 2018). In particular, we searched for flow analogues of each day of the June 2017 heatwave and reconstructed the associated daily Tmax anomalies over southwestern Europe (SWE; black box in Fig. 1a). Following previous studies (e.g. Sousa et al., 2018), the roles of SM and SST in the reconstructed Tmax anomalies were considered by distinguishing between analogues preceded by dry/wet conditions over the same region and by high/low SST values over the WM during the previous 15 days (full details of the methodology are given in Section S1 of the supplementary material). Fig. 1b shows that the Tmax over Iberia is substantially higher (around 2 °C) for flow analogues of the June 2017 heatwave (light grey boxplots) than for random circulation conditions (dark grey boxplots), illustrating the large contribution of the atmospheric circulation in driving the extreme temperatures. Moreover, we find that flow analogues of the June 2017 heatwave often trigger warmer conditions when preceded by

dry conditions. The warming is even higher if these dry conditions occur with high SST values over the WM (~ + 1 °C higher than that inferred from the rest of possible preceding conditions; i.e. wet SWE & hot WM, wet SWE & cold WM, and dry SWE & cold WM). Although these results are closely linked to this particular event, the effect of atmospheric circulation, SM and Mediterranean SST on Iberian temperature is also observed to a greater or lesser degree for other major heatwaves affecting Iberia (not shown).

Following the previous analysis and the bibliographic review described in the Introduction, we construct Iberian storylines of the summer (June-to-August, JJA) change in mean Tmax (hereinafter, Iberian warming; IW) by investigating the forced response (future minus baseline) of these three drivers:

- Iberian geopotential height change (IZ500). Mean summer Z500* change averaged in the [35°–45°N, 10°W–5°E] domain. As in Grise (2022), Z500* is defined as the Z500 with the zonal mean removed, which helps to identify the positions of troughs and ridges in the mid-tropospheric flow and emphasises regional dynamical changes by removing first-order thermodynamic effects of GW in Z500 (large-scale expansion of the troposphere).
- Iberian soil moisture change (ISM). Mean summer SM change averaged in the [35°–45°N, 10°W–5°E] domain.
- Western Mediterranean sea surface temperature change (WMSST). Mean summer SST change averaged in the [35°–45°N, 6°W–12°E] domain.

All spatial averages are area-weighted. The domains used for the definition of these three drivers (Fig. 2) are defined in the most general way possible in order to encompass all kinds of situations affecting Iberia (including the specific event of June 2017 as well as other heatwave episodes). While IZ500 is computed using the whole spatial domain of Iberia indicated in Fig. 2, IW is calculated using only the land grid cells within this region. Additional analyses confirm that the conclusions drawn from the results presented in this work are not sensitive to the choice of the domains over Iberia and the Mediterranean Sea (not shown).

To evaluate the reliability of Iberian Tmax and the three drivers in GCMs, we have compared their JJA values in historical simulations with those in ERA5 reanalysis during the 1981–2011 period (Fig. S2). Overall, the analysed variables compare relatively well between reanalysis and GCMs. The multi-model median is reasonably close to the mean of the ERA5 reanalysis for Iberian Tmax and the three drivers. Although there are GCMs with large biases, most of them are within the range of two standard deviations from the ERA5 mean.

2.3. Storyline methodology

The generation of the storylines has been carried out following the methodology developed by Zappa and Shepherd (2017). Firstly, we have computed for each individual GCM realization the climate change responses of the previously introduced drivers, which are defined as the difference between the 2070–2100 and 1981–2011 means. Then, the summer temperature response (ΔT_{max}) is modelled separately for each grid cell using a multi-linear regression model (MLRM) on the summer response of the three drivers scaled by the GW (defined as the change in global mean near-surface annual temperature, ΔT):

$$\frac{\Delta T_{max_{sm}}}{\Delta T_m} = a_x + b_x \cdot \left(\frac{IZ500}{\Delta T}\right)'_m + c_x \cdot \left(\frac{ISM}{\Delta T}\right)'_m + d_x \cdot \left(\frac{WMSST}{\Delta T}\right)'_m \quad (1)$$

The vertical dash ' indicates the standardised anomaly relative to the MMM, the intercept a_x represents the MMM of ΔT_{max} , and the b_x, c_x, d_x regression coefficients give the sensitivity of ΔT_{max} to each of the drivers used in the regression analysis, IZ500, ISM and WMSST, respectively. Scaling the responses of the three drivers by GW avoids

Fig. 1. a) Daily maximum temperature (Tmax) anomalies (with respect to 1981–2010; K) averaged over the June 2017 heatwave (10–23 June 2017). The black box delimits the southwestern Europe (SWE) domain. b) Flow-conditioned (light grey boxes) and random (dark grey boxes) distributions of the spatially-averaged detrended Tmax anomaly over SWE (K) for the June 2017 heatwave preceded by wet SWE and hot Western Mediterranean (WM), wet SWE and cold WM, dry SWE and hot WM, and dry SWE and cold WM. The boxes extend from the lower (Q1) to the upper (Q3) quartile values of the data, with a horizontal line indicating the position of the median (Q2). The whiskers extend from the boxes to show the range of the data between the 10th and 90th percentiles. The horizontal solid red line represents the spatially-averaged detrended Tmax anomaly over SWE for the June 2017 heatwave. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Spatial domains used to define the drivers of the climate change response in summer temperature within the storyline approach: Western Mediterranean sea surface temperature (WMSST; purple box), Iberian geopotential height (IZ500) and Iberian soil moisture (ISM; red box). While IZ500 is computed using the whole spatial domain of Iberia, Iberian warming (IW) is calculated using only the land grid cells within this region. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

multicollinearity between some drivers in the MLRMs (Table S2). As the scaled driver responses are no longer significantly correlated in the multi-model ensemble, it is reasonable to assume that they are influenced by independent sources of uncertainty.

Once the sensitivity coefficients (a_x, b_x, c_x, d_x) are computed, one can obtain the Tmax change for given values of global warming (ΔT_m) and driver responses ($(IZ500/\Delta T)'_m, (ISM/\Delta T)'_m, (WMSST/\Delta T)'_m$). The anomalies in the driver responses are intentionally selected to have the same standardised amplitude. This value is referred to as storyline index t and represents the magnitude of the driver responses ($t = (IZ500/\Delta T)'_m = (ISM/\Delta T)'_m = (WMSST/\Delta T)'_m$). In general, large (positive or negative) values of this index indicate extreme driver responses, while values close to zero denote responses close to the MMM. Substituting t in the previous equation, the Tmax response can thus be expressed as:

$$\frac{\Delta T_{max_x}}{\Delta T} = a_x + t \cdot (b_x + c_x + d_x) \quad (2)$$

The storylines are generated by the combination of different (typically extreme) driver responses compared to the MMM. Thus, considering two possible ‘states’ (strong or weak climate response) for each of the N drivers, the number of storylines would be 2^N . In this work, we adopt the common practice within the storyline methodology of using just two drivers. This way, the resulting four storylines ensure enough diversity to explain most of the inter-model variability of the Iberian warming while keeping the simplicity in the interpretation that would be lost for a high number of storylines. In particular, the storylines are generated from the two drivers with the largest influence on Iberian warming (i.e. those two drivers with the largest absolute values of the associated regression coefficients over Iberia). This way:

$$\frac{\Delta T_{max_x}}{\Delta T} = a_x \pm D1_x \cdot t \pm D2_x \cdot t \quad (3)$$

where $D1$ and $D2$ are the coefficients associated with the two chosen drivers (i.e. two out of the three coefficients b_x, c_x and d_x in Eq. 2).

In order to construct plausible yet extreme storylines, as Zappa and Shepherd (2017), the storyline index is chosen to lie on the 80 % confidence region of the joint distribution of the driver responses. For example, for the ISM and IZ500 drivers, this means that the storylines are evaluated where the lines $(IZ500/\Delta T)'_m = (ISM/\Delta T)'_m$ and $(IZ500/\Delta T)'_m = -(ISM/\Delta T)'_m$ intercept the ellipse of 80 % confidence, which is obtained by fitting a bivariate normal distribution to the GCM responses. Since the correlation between the drivers are low (Table S2),

the confidence region can be well approximated by the ellipse (circle) with the form:

$$\left[\left(\frac{IZ500}{\Delta T} \right)'_m \right]^2 + \left[\left(\frac{ISM}{\Delta T} \right)'_m \right]^2 = \chi^2(0.8, 2) \quad (4)$$

with $\chi^2(p, k)$ being the quantile function of the chi-squared distribution with k degrees of freedom evaluated at probability p . Considering the equality in the amplitude of the driver responses $t = (IZ500/\Delta T)'_m = (ISM/\Delta T)'_m$, the storyline index takes the value $t = \sqrt{\chi^2(0.8, 2)}/2 \sim 1.27$. The storyline methodology employed in this work was developed by Zappa and Shepherd (2017), where full details are provided, and further information can be found in Appendix A of Mindlin et al. (2020).

3. Results

3.1. Multi-model mean and variability of future projected changes

Despite the large climate variability due to a complex orography and a geographical situation between the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea, Iberia is overall characterised by hot and dry summers (Figs. S3a and S3c). The prevailing weather conditions are anticyclonic (Cortesi et al., 2014) and are strongly influenced by the subtropical high-pressure belt associated with the Azores High, which extends its influence to the north of Iberia (Fig. S3b; De Castro et al., 2005; Mora and Vieira, 2020). The average summer SSTs of the Mediterranean Sea are high, with the eastern basin warmer than the western one (Fig. S3d). Beyond the geographic situation (the eastern basin is further south than the western one), complex currents, upwelling and other factors also contribute to this SST difference (Millot, 1999; Lionello et al., 2012).

By the end of the 21st century, the MMM projects an increase in Tmax and a decrease in SM over Europe in general and over Iberia in particular. Southern and central Europe are expected to experience larger warming and soil drying than northern Europe (Fig. 3a and c). On the other hand, the projected MMM differences in Z500* suggest an increase in the frequency and/or intensity of high-pressure systems over southern Europe and a decrease over northern Europe (Fig. 3b). Finally, oceans warm up slower than land, with the projected change in SST of the Mediterranean Sea being substantially larger than that of the North Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 3d). This land-sea warming contrast has been previously reported in other studies and is attributed to multiple (non-independent) factors, including differences between land and sea in terms of thermal inertia (Manabe et al., 1992), moisture availability (Sutton

Fig. 3. Multi-model mean (MMM) changes of summer (JJA) mean a) maximum temperature (T_{max} ; K), b) Geopotential height at 500 hPa with zonal mean removed ($Z500^*$; m), c) soil moisture (SM; kg m^{-2}), and d) sea surface temperature (SST; K) for the 2070–2100 period of the SSP5–8.5 scenario with respect to 1981–2011 of the historical simulation.

et al., 2007), and lapse rate (Joshi et al., 2008).

The MMM serves as a benchmark, representing a central estimate of model behaviour within the CMIP6 dataset. However, it does not inform on the diversity of projected changes among the GCMs and may not even represent a physically meaningful response. Fig. 4 displays the spread among the GCM projected changes (2070–2100 minus 1981–2011) of GW, as well as the summer responses in IW, and the drivers, namely IZ500, ISM and WMSST. Overall, all of them are characterised by large inter-model spread. Despite the agreement on the sign of the T_{max}

change, the differences among the GCMs with the largest and smallest warmings are around $3\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for GW, IW and WMSST. Similarly, all GCMs project a drying trend over Iberia, but the magnitude of the SM changes is rather uncertain, as indicated by the interquartile range of $\sim 1.5\text{ kg/m}^2$. Finally, although most GCMs project an increase in $Z500^*$ over Iberia (the whole interquartile range has positive values), some of them indicate small changes or even a slight decrease. To account for these uncertainties and understand the influence of the three drivers on IW, in the next sections we apply the storyline approach described in Section 2.3.

Fig. 4. Spread of climate change responses (2070–2100 minus 1981–2011) simulated by the CMIP6 models under the SSP5–8.5 scenario: Global warming (GW; K), Iberian warming (IW; K), Iberian geopotential height change (IZ500; m), Iberian soil moisture change (ISM; kg m^{-2}) and Western Mediterranean SST (WMSST; K). GW is evaluated based on annual means, while the other indicators are evaluated for summer. See the caption of Fig. 1 for the definition of boxplots.

3.2. Temperature sensitivity to the drivers

As described in Section 2.3, MLRMs are applied for each grid cell to assess the future change in summer T_{max} based on the response of the three drivers scaled by GW (see Eq. 1). As expected due to the scrutinised selection of IW drivers, the best performance of the regression framework is found over Iberia and the western Mediterranean Sea, with values in the coefficients of determination (R^2) up to 0.8–0.9 (Fig. S4). These values indicate that the three drivers control most of the inter-model spread of IW. Although the consideration of other climate change drivers in the regression framework could increase the explained variance (see discussion in Section 4.1), this improvement would be rather small given the already good performance of the MLRMs.

Fig. 5 illustrates the values of the regression coefficients obtained from the MLRMs, which allow us to characterise the sensitivity of ΔT_{max} to each of the driver responses. The significant positive values for IZ500 over Iberia and northwestern Africa (Fig. 5a) indicate that an anomalously high geopotential height in the multi-model ensemble

Fig. 5. Sensitivities of summer changes in maximum temperature (ΔT_{max} , 2070–2100 minus 1981–2011) associated with the uncertainties in the climate change responses of the drivers: a) IZ500, b) ISM and c) WMSST. These sensitivities correspond to the coefficients obtained from Eq. 1 (b_x for IZ500, c_x for ISM and d_x for WMSST). Colours show the T_{max} responses scaled by GW (K/K) due to one standard deviation positive anomaly of the driver response with respect to the MMM. Stippling indicates regions where the regression coefficients are statistically significant at 10 % level (two-tailed t -test).

tends to enhance the IW. In particular, the largest values are found in western Iberia. This is in line with [Sousa et al. \(2018\)](#), who reported positive temperature anomalies over this region when subtropical high-pressure systems occur in the 15° – 0° W longitudinal band (see their Fig. S2). On the other hand, ISM negatively correlates with ΔT_{max} across southern Europe and particularly over the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 5b). Accordingly, the larger the projected decrease in SM over Iberia, the larger the T_{max} increase there, consistent with the expected behaviour of land-atmosphere coupling in transitional regions ([Miralles et al., 2019](#); [Soares et al., 2019](#)). Finally, enhanced warming over the western Mediterranean Sea in the multi-model ensemble is linked to an increase in ΔT_{max} across some parts of northern Africa and at certain European coastal locations. However, the warming over inland Iberia is barely influenced by the magnitude of the WMSST response (Fig. 5c).

3.3. Storylines

We have constructed four storylines of future changes in summer T_{max} based on the combination of IZ500 and ISM, the two most influential drivers of IW according to Fig. 5. These two leading drivers are not unexpected, as atmospheric circulation and SM usually explains a larger portion of T_{max} increase during heatwaves over Iberia than SST (see e.g. Fig. 1). Fig. 6 illustrates the range of the two driver responses in the CMIP6 ensemble as well as the magnitude of the anomalies chosen to generate the storylines (represented by black stars) following the regression framework described in Section 2.3. Each storyline is characterised by a combination of high or low IZ500 and high or low ISM

(see Eq. 3, with $D1_x$ and $D2_x$ being respectively b_x and c_x). The resulting summer ΔT_{max} for the four storylines are illustrated in Fig. 7 along with the MMM. The storylines characterised by the largest and smallest warmings over most of Europe and northern Africa result from the combinations of high IZ500 (2.6 m K^{-1}) + low ISM ($-1.1 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and low IZ500 (-0.7 m K^{-1}) + high ISM ($-0.5 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$), respectively. Note that the terms high and low here are relative to the MMM (Fig. 7c), but they do not necessarily imply changes in the same sign in the drivers. Accordingly, a high (low) IZ500 indicates a strong increase (small decrease) in anticyclonic activity over Iberia, while a high (low) ISM represents a weak (strong) drying compared to the MMM. The other two storylines describe T_{max} responses of intermediate amplitude.

For the particular case of Iberia, while the combination of low IZ500 + high ISM (Fig. 7d) is associated with IW values of ~ 1.4 – 1.7 K/K , those obtained for the combination of high IZ500 + low ISM (Fig. 7b) reach up to $\sim 2.5 \text{ K/K}$. Fig. S5 shows the deviation of each storyline with respect to the multi-model mean to better visualize the differences over Iberia among the storylines. Although both drivers contribute to this difference, IZ500 is the main responsible, as inferred from the comparison of the storylines with high and low IZ500. The storylines characterised by a high IZ500 (Fig. 7a and b) show higher warmings over Iberia than those characterised by low IZ500 (Fig. 7d and e) regardless of the response in ISM.

In addition, we have also repeated the analysis depicted in Fig. 7 but using a composite approach instead of the regression framework. To do so, we have averaged the scaled ΔT_{max} for the GCMs with similar driver responses, which are those delimited by the four quadrants of Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. ISM ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$) against IZ500 (m K^{-1}) driver responses scaled by GW for individual GCMs. The black stars indicate the selected four storylines that combine anomalies in the driver responses. The dashed ellipses show the 80 % confidence region obtained by fitting a bivariate normal distribution to the GCM responses (Eq. 4). The quadrants delimited by the inner ellipse and by the four straight lines define the regions used to group the GCMs according to the four storylines.

Fig. 7. Climate change response in summer Tmax per degree of GW (K/K) according to (a,b,d,e) four plausible storylines of climate change that are conditioned on the IZ500 and ISM responses. The storylines in a) and b) are characterised by high IZ500 compared to the MMM, while those in d) and e) have low IZ500. The storylines in a) and d) have high ISM, while those in b) and e) have low ISM compared to the MMM. c) MMM response in Tmax scaled by GW (K/K). The corresponding driver responses in each storyline are indicated by the four black stars in Fig. 6. Values in parentheses represent the IW for each storyline.

GCMs within the inner ellipse have not been considered in the analysis because of their proximity to the MMM. The resulting spatial distributions (Fig. S6) resemble those derived with the regression framework (Fig. 7), supporting the previous findings.

The four storylines show that both the magnitude and the spatial distribution of the Tmax warming over Iberia are strongly dependent on the response of specific drivers, which is hidden when only the MMM is considered. Following this, now we conduct more in-depth analyses for this particular region. First, we compare the projected IW across storylines and each individual CMIP6 model (Fig. 8a). Overall, the range of the projected summer IW by the storylines encompasses most of the inter-model variability, indicating that the two drivers employed to generate the storylines (i.e. IZ500 and ISM) largely account for the uncertainty in IW. In addition, the fact that the storylines are within the CMIP6 distribution confirms that they are plausible and physically self-consistent realisations of future climate.

Note that storylines ignore the role of GW in the uncertainty on regional projections. To explicitly account for the GW influence on the temporal evolution of IW, the scaled summer IW of each storyline (Eq. 3) and CMIP6 model has been multiplied by the MMM GW of each year (using a moving 31-year window) of the 1981–2100 period (Fig. 8b). As expected, the amplitude of the projected IW follows that of GW. In addition, the inter-storyline variability of IW also gradually increases with GW, ranging between 7 and 9 °C across the storylines for the end of the 21st century.

Although feasible, the retrieved projections are tied to somewhat arbitrary choices of the magnitude of the driver responses. In order to get the full picture of driver responses, Fig. 8c displays the IW as a function of GW and the storyline index (t) for the combination of driver responses associated with the highest storyline uncertainty (see Eq. 3). In particular, values of GW range from 0 to 4.5 °C and values of the

Fig. 8. a) Climate change response (2070–2100 minus 1981–2011) in summer IW (i.e. ΔT_{max}) per degree of GW (K/K) for each CMIP6 model (colour circles) and the four storylines (empty colour squares). The black star represents the MMM, and the grey-shaded area comprises one standard deviation. b) Time evolution of the summer IW (K; with respect to the 1981–2011 mean) for the CMIP6 ensemble and the four storylines. The solid black line represents the MMM, and the dashed lines show the 5th and 95th percentiles of the ensemble. c) Projected changes of summer IW (K) as a function of GW and the storyline index. The index represents the standardised anomaly of the combined response of IZ500 and ISM, with positive values indicating high IZ500 and low ISM compared to those of the MMM, and vice versa. More details on the storyline index are provided in Section 2.3.

storyline index from -1.5 and 1.5 , which are reasonable based on the projections of the multi-model ensemble. As introduced in Section 2.3, the storyline index represents the standardised anomaly in the driver responses, and it has been constructed to represent the combination of drivers yielding the best / worst case scenarios. This way, positive (negative) values of the storyline index indicate high (low) IZ500 and low (high) ISM values compared to the MMM responses, therefore yielding the largest (smallest) IW across the multi-model ensemble. The spread of IW across the range of GW is larger than those of the storyline index. Despite this, the sensitivity of IW to changes in IZ500 and ISM is still quite strong. As an illustration, for a 4 °C GW, which is close to the multi-model median for the end of the 21st century (Fig. 4), the IW ranges from ~ 6.5 °C to ~ 8.5 °C depending on the storyline.

4. Discussion

4.1. Selection of climate change drivers

To test the suitability of the drivers' selection, we have repeated the sensitivity analysis shown in Fig. 5 but considering additional drivers that also exert a clear influence on regional temperature and show large uncertainty in future projections: the southwestern Europe cloud cover change (SWCC), the ratio between the tropical and Arctic warming (RTAW) and the North Atlantic SST change (NATLSSST). In Europe,

cloud-temperature interactions have an important role in the uncertainties of climate change summer projections over large parts of the continent. In particular, GCMs characterised by stronger present-day anti-correlation between cloud cover and temperature over land tend to simulate larger future decreases in cloud cover (Boé and Terray, 2014). On the other hand, there are well-established remote drivers of the summer atmospheric circulation responses to climate change over Europe. In this section, we use two climate change drivers previously employed for the construction of storylines: RTAW and NATLSST. RTAW measures the differential warming rate between tropical and Arctic latitudes. An enhanced warming in the Arctic compared to the tropics is related to a reduction in equator-to-pole meridional temperature gradients, resulting in a weakened storm track and an equatorward shift in the mid-latitude jet, with important implications for summer European climate (Coumou et al., 2018). NATLSST is in turn associated with the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), which has experienced a slowdown during the last decades (e.g. Rahmstorf et al., 2015). This slowdown has led to anomalously cold SSTs around the subpolar gyre, which have been linked to a summer weakening of westerlies over the North Atlantic sector as well as to persistent dry and hot extremes in Europe (Haarsma et al., 2015; Rahmstorf et al., 2015). Herein, SWCC is defined as the cloud cover change averaged in the [35°–52°N, 10°W–9°E] domain (southwestern Europe); RTAW is computed from regional averages of temperature change in the tropical upper troposphere (30°S–30°N at 250 hPa) and Arctic lower troposphere (60°–90°N at 850 hPa) (following Peings et al., 2018 and Garrido-Perez et al., 2022); and NATLSST is the SST change averaged in the [50°–65°N, 40°–10°W] domain (the subpolar gyre; following Rahmstorf et al., 2015 and Garrido-Perez et al., 2022).

Fig. S7 shows the values of the regression coefficients obtained from the MLRMs, which allow us to identify the drivers with the largest influence on summer ΔT_{max} . Overall, the three new drivers (NATLSST, SWCC and RTAW; Fig. S7d-f) exhibit considerably smaller values over Iberia than any of the original drivers (IZ500, ISM and WMSST; Fig. S7a-c) (Table S3). Notably, the impact of the three new drivers on ΔT_{max} is not significant across most of the Iberian region. While there might be other potential drivers not considered herein, this finding cautions against the inclusion of the new drivers and reinforces the original selection.

As ISM also responds to regional circulation changes, its response might be influenced by concurrent changes in atmospheric circulation. Under these circumstances, the variance of summer IW explained by this driver would be inflated by coupled changes with the atmospheric circulation. In order to examine this, we have constructed storylines of Z500* based on the response of ISM. Overall, the explained variance of Z500* is very low, and the resulting circulation anomalies exhibit comparable patterns, with small deviations from the multi-model mean (not shown). This result indicates that the ISM response is not tied to those in circulation, and hence their influence on summer IW primarily involves thermodynamic effects. In fact, ISM is not significantly correlated with IZ500, both before and after scaling their responses by GW (Table S2), evidencing again the detachment from the circulation response.

4.2. Extreme temperatures

It is expected that a warming in summer mean T_{max} will result in an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme heat events, but the magnitude of these trends may not exhibit a linear correspondence. Understanding regional trends of extreme heat events is essential for providing valuable insights into their impacts on both biophysical and human systems, and for developing strategies to mitigate and adapt to these effects. Similarly to the approach in Zappa and Shepherd (2017) for windiness, here we quantify extreme heat as the 95th percentile of the T_{max} for each summer season (T_{max95x}). Following this, we have repeated the sensitivity analyses for the three summer drivers (i.e. those

shown in Fig. 5) but considering T_{max95x} instead of the summer average of T_{max} (Fig. S8). Overall, the responses of T_{max} and T_{max95x} are similar for the considered drivers, the main difference being found for JJA IZ500, which is associated with a generally smaller response in T_{max95x} than in T_{max} .

Besides T_{max95x} , more complex metrics have been employed to characterise the changes in extreme temperatures. First, we have repeated the sensitivity analyses but considering the 95th percentile of the 15-day mean T_{max} of each summer. By doing so, we focused on the characteristic timescales of heatwave events (see e.g. the June 2017 heatwave in Fig. 1). Overall, only relatively minor changes have been found in the magnitude and spatial distribution of the responses to each driver (Fig. S9), which further corroborates our previous findings.

Interestingly, the influence of the driver responses weakens to non-significant levels for more elaborated heatwave metrics (not shown). These metrics include the frequency and cumulative intensity (sum of exceedances over a threshold) of heatwave events, defined as periods when T_{max} is above the 95th percentile of the 15-day moving window of the 1981–2011 climatology for at least three consecutive days. These results are not completely surprising, as previous studies have already reported that the projected changes in warm extremes depend on the index considered (e.g. Sillmann et al., 2013), so does for the storylines. One potential explanation could be that the linearity assumption associated with the storyline approach (see Section 4.3) may not hold when dealing with complex metrics like those mentioned for heatwaves. Moreover, in addition to changes in the mean, heatwave projections are strongly affected by changes in variance, which are not accounted for in the storyline of summer mean T_{max} , but could be important in regions of pronounced feedbacks (e.g. land-atmosphere coupling), such as Europe (Vogel et al., 2017; Di Luca et al., 2020). In particular, heatwave metrics demanding a minimum persistence of T_{max} values above an upper tail threshold are expected to be sensitive to changes in variability. This hypothesis is supported by Table S4, which shows the MMM changes in both the mean and standard deviation of Iberian T_{max} scaled by GW for the four groups of CMIP6 GCMs employed for the composite of Fig. S6. Interestingly, the group of GCMs characterised by high ISM and low IZ500 exhibits the lowest changes in the mean but the second highest in the variability of T_{max} . Although further research is needed, our results suggest that our storylines might be more suitable to characterise the uncertainty of projections in extreme temperature indices that are strongly influenced by changes in the mean, but not in variability.

4.3. Linearity assumption

Zappa and Shepherd (2017) already discussed and tested the robustness of the storyline approach to some issues and assumptions, including the potential influence of outlying GCMs and internal climate variability in the multi-model ensemble, the pattern scaling assumption or the linear additivity assumption associated with the use of MLRMs (see their discussion and supplementary material). In particular, these authors argue that the similarity in outcomes between the non-linear composite approach and the linear regression framework (see Section 3.3 and Figs. 7 and S6 herein) is indicative of the linear combination of driver responses when building the storylines. In order to examine this in more detail, we have employed a generalised additive model (GAM) (Servén and Brummitt, 2018), which is a semi-parametric extension of the generalised linear model and an effective tool for conducting non-linear regression analyses (e.g. Garrido-Perez et al., 2021). Since this kind of complex model requires a large amount of data to avoid overfitting, we have extended the sample size used for the MLRMs, which was originally limited to the climate response (for the 2070–2100 period) of 25 CMIP6 GCMs (see Table S1). To do so, we have considered all possible 31-year windows (i.e. periods of 31 consecutive years) within the 1981–2100 period and computed their climate responses with respect to 1981–2011. In addition to enable the use of GAMs, this

larger sample size makes the results less sensitive to potential outliers. The consideration of different periods within the same GCM should not be problem since climate responses are always scaled by GW within the storyline approach. In fact, this approach ensures that the results are robust to the choice of the period employed to assess the climate change signal, reducing the reliance on the pattern scaling assumption. Despite this, it is important to note that early 31-year windows exhibit greater uncertainty in climate response estimates due to the scaling. This is because the scaling affects both to the forced response and the residual internal variability. While the magnitude of the variability remains relatively constant with time before scaling, its scaled contribution increases more for early 31-year windows with smaller global warming.

Fig. 9 illustrates the partial dependence plots of ΔT_{max} for a location in inland Iberia. These partial dependence plots depict the effect of each of the three drivers used to construct the storylines (independent variables) on the predicted change in maximum temperature (ΔT_{max} , dependent variable). To create a partial dependence plot, the model fixes all other driver variables to their mean values. Then, it calculates the average predicted change in ΔT_{max} for each possible value of the chosen driver variable. As in the GAM models, these plots have been generated through the PyGam python package (Servén and Brummitt, 2018). The resulting plot shows how the average ΔT_{max} responds to changes in the driver, revealing whether the relationship is or not linear. As expected, an increase (decrease) in IZ500 or WMSST (ISM) results in an increase of T_{max} warming, in agreement with the results obtained from the linear regression framework. In addition, we find overall linear relationships between the climate change responses of T_{max} and of the three drivers, except for extreme values. As an illustration, a negative linear relationship is identified between -1 and 2 for ISM, but this trend is much steeper for higher values. A similar behaviour is observed for WMSST since the positive linear relationship abruptly changes to much steeper rates for values below ~ -1.5 . Although these results suggest the existence of potential non-linear interactions for extreme values of the driver responses, the nonlinearity could also be an effect of a poor fit of the GAM caused by outliers or limited sample size at these extreme ranges.

Given the reasonably linear relationships between summer IW and the three driver responses, we have also repeated the storyline analyses using MLRMs on the new extended sample. Although the resulting explained variance is lower compared to that obtained from the reduced dataset due to increased variability and the identified non-linearities, the spatial patterns of ΔT_{max} are similar to those reported in Section 3, and show even stronger sensitivities to the three driver responses (compare Fig. S10 with Fig. 5), strengthening our earlier conclusions.

Future work on storylines could benefit from this data extension approach (i.e. using different time intervals to compute the climate responses) and use not only MLRMs to build the storylines but also more complex models that take into account non-linear relationships. Besides the GAMs employed in this section, multiple statistical and machine

learning techniques may contribute to explain a larger fraction of the inter-model uncertainty and identify more robustly the climate change drivers shaping the regional projections.

4.4. Feedback between regional warming and thermodynamic drivers

The use of the summer season to compute the climate responses of both the IW and the drivers in the storyline approach complicates the interpretation of the results because of the slowly-varying character of the drivers and its coupling with temperature. Low SM and high SSTs can act both as a driver of heatwaves and/or a response to high air temperatures, which makes it difficult to separate cause (driver) and effect (IW). In order to avoid this, we have repeated the storyline analyses (i.e. those shown in Figs. 5–8) but considering the previous spring (MAM) instead of the concurrent summer (JJA) conditions to compute the ISM and WMSST drivers (JJA IZ500 remains unchanged because of its fast responses). Overall, the resulting spatial patterns of summer T_{max} warming induced by these driver responses (Fig. S11) are similar to those of Fig. 5. However, as a consequence of the seasonal lag and potential feedbacks, the sensitivity of summer IW to MAM ISM and MAM WMSST is considerably lower than to JJA ISM and JJA WMSST. In fact, the influence of ISM on summer ΔT_{max} over Iberia (Fig. 5) is no longer significant when considering the spring ISM instead (Fig. S11). The lack of significance could be due to limited sample size since we obtain a substantial significant response of summer Iberian IW to MAM ISM for the extended data sample described in Section 4.3 (Fig. S12). This result confirms that summer IW depends on the future response of SM even removing the potential feedbacks that might be affecting this relationship.

5. Summary and concluding remarks

The main goal of this study is to construct storylines of the future summer warming over Iberia, by using historical and future simulations of an ensemble of global climate models from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6. These storylines are generated from the simulated climate change responses in atmospheric circulation, regional soil moisture content and Mediterranean sea surface temperature, which are known drivers of future summer warming. Unlike previous studies that typically rely on remote drivers of the atmospheric circulation to construct storylines of a given indicator (Garrido-Perez et al., 2022; Mindlin et al., 2020, 2021; Schmidt and Grise, 2021; Ghosh and Shepherd, 2023; Monerie et al., 2023), the drivers used herein exert direct regional influences on the targeted variable, sometimes being coupled to it through well-known feedbacks. As another novelty with respect to the existing literature (mainly biased towards winter dynamic variables such as precipitation and wind patterns), our research addresses thermodynamic aspects of climate change, which are comparatively more robust but still uncertain and of high concern. In particular,

Fig. 9. Partial dependence plots of the drivers used in the generalised additive model (GAM) for a selected grid point in Iberia [41.25°N, 2.5°E] and summer. Red dotted lines indicate the 95 % confidence intervals for the estimated functions (blue solid lines). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

we focus on maximum temperature during the summer season, when the impacts of high temperatures are the largest, paying special attention to Iberia, where the highest warming is projected in Europe.

The main findings of this paper can be summarised as follows:

- The multi-model mean projection for summer at the end of the 21st century indicates an increase in temperature and a decrease in soil moisture over Europe in general and especially over Iberia. The Mediterranean Sea is projected to experience a marked warming, although less pronounced than in the continent. There are also hints of an increase in the frequency of high-pressure systems over southern Europe and a decrease over northern Europe. However, at least in Iberia, the magnitude, and sometimes even the sign, of these changes are characterised by great uncertainty.
- Multiple linear regression models based on the summer responses of regional drivers (geopotential height, soil moisture and western Mediterranean sea surface temperatures) explain most of the inter-model variability of Iberian warming, with coefficients of determination up to 0.8–0.9 at some locations.
- The magnitude of the projected soil moisture deficits and anticyclonic circulation enhancement contributes the most to modulate future changes in Iberian warming. The relationship between the western Mediterranean Sea warming and the amplified warming in Iberia is weaker than for the other two drivers.
- The magnitude of the future summer warming over Iberia depend to a varying extent on the evolution of these drivers. The range of summer warming projected by extreme, but feasible, storylines encompasses most of the inter-model variability, with differences of up to 0.5 K/K (~2 °C for the end of the 21st century). The combination of pronounced (moderate) Iberian drying together with a high (low) ridging activity causes the largest (smallest) warmings of the considered storylines.
- Similar conclusions are obtained for simple indicators of extremely warm summer periods. However, the results vary with the considered index, arguably due to varying influences of changes in mean and variability. In particular, for more complex heatwave metrics, the amount of the projected uncertainty that can be explained by a simple linear combination of the aforementioned driver responses is largely reduced, suggesting inadequacies of the storyline approach (e.g. linear assumption) or of the considered drivers.
- An assessment of the linearity assumption demonstrates that the influence of the summer driver responses on the magnitude of the projected changes is fairly linear, except for the most extreme changes in the drivers. The data extension approach employed in this analysis paves the way for novel methodologies in constructing storylines of more complex regional climate impact indicators, which require extensive sample sizes to characterise non-linear dependencies.

In short, we have been able to explain to a great extent the large uncertainty of summer temperature projections over Iberia based on the future evolution of three climate change drivers associated with regional atmospheric ridging and soil moisture stress, and western Mediterranean warming. Although the observed climatological features of these drivers are reasonably well reproduced by the climate models during the historical period, recent studies have reported that climate models are not able to accurately reproduce recent warming trends in Europe (van Oldenborgh et al., 2009; Fischer et al., 2021; Vautard et al., 2023). Overall, climate models warm less over western Europe than recorded during the historical period, which has been attributed to biases in the simulated trend of the atmospheric circulation over the Euro-Atlantic sector (Boé et al., 2020; Vautard et al., 2023). If this underestimated warming were to carry over future projections, our worst-case storyline (dry soil and more frequent anticyclonic activity) would potentially be even warmer than current projections. In fact, the inclusion of the models previously excluded due to driver responses clearly beyond the

ensemble distribution to the analyses (see Section 2.1) result in even drier and warmer storylines than those reported throughout the manuscript (not shown). This increased warming could have significant implications for the associated impacts and the design of strategic adaptation and mitigation plans.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jose M. Garrido-Perez: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis. **David Barriopedro:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Ricardo M. Trigo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Pedro M.M. Soares:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Giuseppe Zappa:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **M. Carmen Álvarez-Castro:** Writing – review & editing. **Ricardo García-Herrera:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2024.107677>.

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